

Congregation of Savigny

also known as "Savigniacs", "Savigniac Order"

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Entry tags: Medieval Christianity, Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Monastic Order, Reform Movement

The Congregation of Savigny grew out of Vital of Mortain's (c. 1060-1122 CE) foundation of a monastery at Savigny in 1113 CE. Vital of Mortain was an itinerant preacher and hermit who retired into the forest near Savigny around 1109 and by 1113 had established a monastery there for his followers. Under Savigny's second abbot, Geoffrey, the congregation experienced rapid expansion and notoriety. In 1147 abbot Serlo of Savigny oversaw the incorporation of the congregation into the Cistercian order.

Date Range: 1113 CE - 1147 CE

Region: Normandy, British Isles

Region tags: Europe, British Isles, Western Europe, France

Anglo-Norman possessions in northern Europe in the twelfth century.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Suydam, Mary. "Origins of the Savignac Order: Savigny's Role within Twelfth-Century Monastic Reform." *Revue Bénédictine*, vol. 86:1-2 (1976): 94-108.
- Source 2: Buhot, Jacqueline. "L'abbaye normande de Savigny, chef d'ordre et fille de Cîteaux," *Le Moyen Âge*, vol. 7 (1936): p. 1-19, 104-121, 178-190, and 249-272.
- Source 3: Swietek, Francis R. and Terrence M. Deneen. "The Episcopal Exemption of Savigny, 1112-1184." *Church History*, vol. 52, no. 3 (1983): 285-298.
- Source 1: Moolenbroek, Jaap van. *Vital l'ermite, prédicateur itinérant, fondateur de l'abbaye normande de Savigny*. Translated from Dutch by Anne-Marie Nambot. Assen/Maastricht, Pays-Bas: 1990.
- Source 2: Conyers, James Patrick. 2001. *Changing habits: The Norman Abbey of Savigny and its Congregation, 1105-1175*. PhD Diss. University of Iowa.
- Source 3: Feiss, Hugh, OSB, Maureen M. O'Brien, and Ronald Pepin, introduction, translators, and editors. *Lives of Monastic Reformers, 2: Abbot Vitalis of Savigny, Abbot Godfrey of Savigny, Peter of Avranches, Blessed Hamo*. Collegeville, Minnesota: Cistercian Publications, 2014.
- Source 1: Hill, Bennett D. *English Cistercian Monasteries and their Patrons in the Twelfth Century*. Urbana, Illinois: University of Illinois Press, 1968.
- Source 2: Reyerson, Kathryn Louis. "The Way of Mary or that of Martha: Conceptions of Monastic life at Savigny, 1112-1180." in *The Medieval Monastery*. St. Cloud, Minnesota: North Star Press, 1988. 34-42.

– Source 3: Hill, Bennett D. "The Beginnings of the First French Foundations of the Norman Abbey of Savigny." *American Benedictine Review*. Vol. 31:1 (1980): 130-152.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Savigny_Abbey
- Source 1 Description: Wikipedia entry on the Abbey of Savigny
- Source 2 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Congregation_of_Savigny
- Source 2 Description: Wikipedia entry on the Congregation of Savigny
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.newadvent.org/cathen/13489b.htm>
- Source 3 Description: Online Catholic Encyclopedia

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=umn.31951002083187s;view=1up;seq=388>
- Source 1 Description: This is a short history of Savigniac monasteries, abbots, and abbesses. Print citation: *Gallia Christiana in provincias ecclesiasticas distributa*, Vol. XI. col. 540e-556d. Paris: 1874.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/histoiredelacon01lavegoog>
- Source 2 Description: This is an institutional history of the Congregation of Savigny written by Dom Claude Auvry between 1698 and 1712. Auvry was a Cistercian monk and abbot of Savigny before he retired to the monastery of his first profession, Les Vaux-de-Cernay, to write this three volume history. Volumes one and two of the three volumes are available on archive.org. Print citation: Auvry, Claude. *Histoire de la congrégation de Savigny*. 3 Vols. Edited by A. Laveille. Paris: A. Picard et Fils, 1896-1898.
- Source 3 URL: <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044004829248;view=1up;seq=373>
- Source 3 Description: This is the edited edition of the hagiographies of Vital of Mortain, the founder of Savigny, and of Godfrey, the second abbot of Savigny. Print citation: Stephen of Fougères. "Vita BB. Vitalis et Gaufridi, primi et secundi abbatum Saviniacensium." Edited by E.P. Sauvage. *Analecta Bollandiana*, Vol. I (1882): p. 355-410.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Congregation of Savigny emerged out of a late eleventh- to early twelfth-century wave of religious enthusiasm that saw the foundation of several new and competing monastic and quasi-monastic groups, such as the Cistercians, Carthusians, and Premonstratensians.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no surviving legislative sources for the Congregation of Savigny, and therefore, there is no information concerning a minimum age for new recruits. Although, after the congregation was incorporated into the Cistercians in 1147 CE, they would likely have adhered to the Cistercian custom that required new recruits to be at least fifteen years old (first enacted in 1134 CE), and then changed to at least eighteen years old in 1154 CE. See Joseph Lynch, "The Cistercians and Underage Novices," *Cîteaux: Commentarii Cistercienses*, vol. 24 (1973): 283-297.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: As far as recruitment, the Congregation of Savigny did not discriminate based on gender, although they segregated their members into all male or female monasteries. Savigny's founder, Vital of Mortain, was part of the eremitical and itinerant preaching movement of the early twelfth century and friends with Robert of Arbrissel and Bernard of

Tiron, all of whom displayed a special interest in the spiritual needs of women. Indeed, it appears that Vital's first monastic establishment was for women, Les Blanches. This house could have been founded as early as 1105 or as late as 1115. Either way, this makes Les Blanches either the first, or among the first, establishments associated with Vital and eventually Savigny. For the issues of dating the establishment of Les Blanches and the evidence for an 1105 foundation, see James Conyers, "Changing habits: The Norman Abbey of Savigny and its Congregation, 1105-1175" (PhD Diss. University of Iowa, 2001) 44-54.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The congregation's new recruits presumably participated in a confirmation ritual, but it is not clear the extent to which it differed from other contemporary monastic confirmation rituals as no legislation survives.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The congregation's founder, Vital of Mortain, was a famous itinerant preacher and hermit.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

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↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Savigniac monasteries collected tithes to support their monasteries, including their building projects. The Congregation attracted wealthy patrons, including royalty from the beginning. They famously bargained to continue accepting tithes after their incorporation into the Cistercians, despite the practice being against Cistercian customs. See specifically chapter three, "The Congregation of Savigny and Its Impact on the Cistercian Order," in Bennett D. Hill's book *English Cistercian Monasteries and their Patrons in the Twelfth Century* (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1968) 80-115. See also Francis R. Swietek and Terrence M. Deneen, "The Episcopal Exemption of Savigny, 1112-1184," *Church History*, Vol. 52, No. 3 (Sep., 1983), pp. 285-298, which revises and updates Hill's work.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Like many medieval monasteries, Savigniac houses might have possessed a variety of exemptions granted by the nobility, bishops, or papacy.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates would have received punishment from episcopal or temporal authorities, not the monastic congregation.

- ↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:
 - Yes
- ↳ Apostates are physically marked as such (e.g. branding, mutilation):
 - No
- ↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punished in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cursed by "high god":
 - Yes
- ↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):
 - Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Congregation of Savigny contained at least thirty-seven monasteries. Two other establishments' membership, Mortemer and La Dunes, in the congregation are disputed.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The monasteries of the congregation were either governed by abbots elected by their own monasteries or overseen by priors answerable to the abbot of their founding house. There is some evidence that Geoffrey of Savigny, the Savigny's second abbot, might have established a general chapter in 1132 CE, where the congregation's other abbots and priors met yearly. At these meetings the abbot of Savigny held the highest authority. For a concise overview on the issue of the establishment of a General Chapter for Savigniac houses, see Conyers, "Changing Habits," 86-90.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: The founder of Savigny, Vital of Mortain, was considered holy and performed miracles. Theoretically any member of the congregation might have performed miracles.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in

choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Rule of Benedict the monks were supposed to be obedient to the orders of the abbot and those above them, but the abbot was to make important decisions in consultation with the whole community.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

- ↳ Revealed by a high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
 - No
- ↳ Inspired by high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
 - No
- ↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
 - No
- ↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
 - No
- ↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
 - No
- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Official interpretation of the Bible came through the Roman hierarchy, though monastic communities often engaged in famously elastic exegesis.
- ↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

- ↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
 - I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

- ↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
 - No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (rare)
Notes: Ideally the members of the congregation adhered to monastic stability and did not often go on pilgrimage.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
 - Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:
– No

↳ Interment:
– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):
– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):
– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Relics or remains might be moved for various reasons, including the deceased desiring to be moved, or for placement in a new tomb or shrine, or because of building projects.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Patrons might join the community just prior to their death in order to be buried on monastic property. Their tombs could also include burials of family members.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Abbots and priors might be buried in other areas of the monastery, like the cloister, church, or chapter house.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents might make supplications and pray to saints or deceased leaders in the community.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: The deity might communicate with adherents during bouts of mystical ecstasy, but this would not be considered possession by the deity.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Scripture

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ |

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This knowledge would have to be granted by the deity.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

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- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
– Yes

↳ Food:
– No

↳ Sacred space(s):
– No

↳ Sacred object(s):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Adultery:
– Yes

↳ Incest:
– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: Being a part of a Christian monastic group requires chastity. Any sexual contact is forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
Notes: Pleasure would likely be in the form of ecstatic mystical experience.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
Notes: Rewards could be in the form of miraculous healing, but sickness could also be figured as a form of blessing, giving the adherent a chance to endure hardship for the glory of the deity.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
Notes: For non-monastic Christians reproductive success could be a reward, but for monks ostensibly devoted to chastity, this was not operative.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:
– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– No
Notes: The second coming of Christ was unknown.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
– No

↳ Other purpose:
– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Yes

Notes: The Congregation of Savigny adhered to the extra moral framework of the monastic Rule of Benedict. While the rule was highly influenced by Christian metaphysical concepts, many of its precepts deal with the mundane, communal life of the monastery.

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - Only specialized religious class

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes

|

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: A certain amount of strength was practically required for agricultural labor and ascetic prowess could be figured as strength.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
– No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Conversion to monastic life entailed a donation to the community.

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Monks were tonsured.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Monasteries were often sites of relief for the immediate region. Furthermore, monks from Savigniac houses periodically left the monastery to care for the sick and perform pastoral duties. See chapter three on the Congregation of Savigny in Bennett D. Hill, 'English Cistercian Monasteries and their Patrons in the Twelfth Century' (Urbana, Illinois: University of Illinois Press, 1968) 80-115, particularly page 93.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Elderly patrons sometimes converted to the group at the end of their lives in order to die as a monk. The monasteries cared for their own elderly, but there is no evidence that Savigniac houses ran institutions like hospitals or hospices during the time covered here.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear, but also seems unlikely that Savigniacs accepted children into their monasteries and, thus, did not run schools. Therefore, any formal education of its members would have occurred prior to their conversion. The education in these monasteries would, then, have been liturgical and pastoral in nature and oriented toward inculcating a monastic lifestyle.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Around 1132 abbot Geoffrey enacted a general chapter and there was a practice of visitation to Savigny's dependent houses. Although, these structures of control and governance failed in practice. See Bennett D. Hill, *English Cistercian Monasteries and their Patrons in the Twelfth Century*, (Urbana,

Illinois: University of Illinois Press, 1968) 90-104. See also, James Patrick Conyers, "Changing habits: The Norman Abbey of Savigny and its congregation, 1105-1175," PhD diss. (University of Iowa, May 2001) 64-95.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Savigniac houses might have provided regional relief.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Notes: Monasteries often provided water management for themselves and their properties. For example, Byland Abbey purportedly had several large ponds, canals, and drainages, however, the surviving twelfth-century archaeological evidence hails from the period after the Congregation of Savigny was incorporated into the Cistercians and therefore tells us little about Savigniac water works. For Cistercian water works see Constance Hoffman Berman, *Medieval Agriculture, the Southern French Countryside, and the Early Cistercians: A Study of Forty-three Monasteries* (Philadelphia: American Philosophical Society, 1986) 87-91. For Byland Abbey see, Marcus Jecock, Andrew Burn, Graham Brown and Al Oswald, *Byland Abbey, Ryedale North Yorkshire: Archaeological survey and investigation of part of the precinct and extra-mural area*. (York, UK: English Heritage Research Department, 2011).

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Savigniac houses received tithes from the community and retained this privilege after their incorporation into the Cistercians (though Cistercian houses were not supposed to take tithes).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Savigniac monasteries were liable for papal tithes, though they could be exempt from these if they gained tithes from the land they owned. See James Patrick Conyers, *Changing habits: The Norman Abbey of Savigny and its congregation, 1105-1175*, PhD diss. (University of Iowa, May 2001) 238-261.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot of Savigny and the general council decided disputes among the dependent monasteries. If disputes could not be settled on this level, bishops could be called in as arbiters.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: The community and/or the abbot could enforce excommunication or exile on those in the community.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Congregation of Savigny was ultimately liable to the papal hierarchy.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Savigniac monasteries followed the Rule of Benedict, but no constitutional documents are extant and possibly never existed. See Bennett D. Hill, *English Cistercian Monasteries and Their Patrons in the Twelfth Century* (Urbana: Illinois University Press, 1968) 86.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Savigniac houses could take tithes or other donations in kind. They also held granges and manors that provided agricultural products for the monasteries.